

Accuracy of physics informed neural network used to model the elastic response of a material

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Abstract

Choosing between theoretical or data-driven models can be a challenge when trying to build accurate and robust physical models. Instead of a clear-cut choice, an interesting approach, called grey-box modelling, consists in combining the two. A main example is the recently introduced Physics Informed Neural Networks (PINNs) framework that allows artificial neural networks (ANN) to be more robust by having them complying to some prior physics laws.

This paper presents how the PINN framework can be applied to continuum mechanics problem and, more precisely, to a boundary value problem on a linear elastic media. A particular choice of architecture and training is motivated and a numerical example is then presented. Different types of networks, ranging from a feedforward network to a residual network (ResNet) with Fourier features, are implemented and compared to a reference finite element model (FEM) solution. The latter model achieves an accuracy of the same order as the FEM with a coefficient of determination $R^2 > 0.999$ between the two solutions.

Introduction

Taking advantage of the constant increase in computing capacities, major progress has been made recently in the field of numerical simulation, so that it is now possible to simulate almost any physical system. These algorithms must be parameterized with material properties to faithfully represent reality. Therefore there is an increasing demand for detailed knowledge of material properties as they affect the accuracy of the results. While traditional methods of determining material properties using tensile tests provide rather limited global information, other methods, such as Digital Image Correlation (DIC), allow to measure a displacement field on the whole domain and thus deliver much richer data. The inverse identification of the material properties can then be achieved using techniques like model updating or the virtual field method.

The idea of this work is to try to apply the newcomer Physics Informed Neural Network (PINNs) model to solve this same inverse identification problem taking uncertainties into account. Introduced in 2019 by Raissi et al. [1], this framework allows neural networks to be more robust by having them complying to some prior physics laws described by partial differential equation (PDE). The PINN is indeed trained to minimize both prediction error and a residual error computed by injecting the neural network in the differential equation using automatic differentiation.

This paper investigate the accuracy of PINNs used to model the elastic response of a material. This is a first necessary step before considering their use for inverse quantification of material properties.

In section 1, we presents how the PINN framework can be applied to continuum mechanics problem. Then we focus on a boundary value problem on a linear elastic media and motivate a particular choice of architecture and training. A numerical application is presented in section 2. Different types of network, ranging from a feedforward network to a residual network (ResNet) with Fourier features, are implemented and compared to a reference finite element model (FEM) solution. The latter model achieves an accuracy of the same order as the FEM with a coefficient of determination $R^2 > 0.999$ between the two solutions.

1 Physics Informed Neural Network framework for boundary value problem in continuum mechanics

In this section, the PINN framework is first introduced in a general way before focusing on a boundary value problem in continuum mechanics.

1.1 Introduction to Physics Informed Neural Networks

Introduced in 2019 by Raissi et al. [1], the Physics Informed Neural Network (PINN) framework is an example of a more general approach called grey box modeling. This approach consists in making data-driven models more robust by having them comply to some prior knowledge of the problem.

In the PINNs framework, the data-driven model is an ANN that gathers the advantages of great approximation capabilities [2], continuity and seamless implementation using a dedicated python package such as PyTorch [3] or TensorFlow [4] for example. An ANN is parameterized by trainable weights (W) and biases (b) and maps an input space X to an output space Y :

$$\mathcal{N}(W, b) : X \mapsto Y \quad (1)$$

In order for the network to be a good approximation of the target function, we must first train it, i.e. find the parameters W and b that minimize the prediction error. This is a complex optimization problem with no analytical solution, that's why heuristic iterative algorithms are commonly used during a training phase. At each iteration the ANN is evaluated on a sample of the domain and compared to the ground truth value to give the residual loss \mathcal{L}_u .

The weights and biases are then updated according to the loss using backpropagation of the gradient. Several sampling strategies are possible as the sample size (called the batch size) and the sampling method (grid, random,...) need to be defined. This is a really standard architecture, more details can be found in [5] for example.

Contrary to classical machine learning where only data is used to train the network, the PINN also needs to comply with some physics laws. There are two main types of these laws: symmetries and ordinary/partial differential equations. These constraints can either be imposed in a hard way by choosing an adequate architecture for the PINN or in a soft way by adding extra terms to the loss function. The next subsection presents how priors from continuum mechanics theory (equations and boundary conditions) can be imposed in a soft way.

1.2 PINNs to model continuum mechanics

1.2.1 Boundary value problem in continuum mechanics

We consider a continuum mechanics boundary value problem. In other words, we seek to determine the displacement and stress field u and σ inside a domain Ω given some boundary conditions, i.e. known values of either u or σ on the boundary of the domain $\delta\Omega$.

These two fields also need to comply to continuum mechanics equations.

The first one is the kinematic relation between displacement and strain ϵ , written as follows in the case of small deformation :

$$\epsilon_{ij} = \frac{1}{2}(u_{i,j} + u_{j,i}) \quad \text{small deformation} \quad (2)$$

The second equation is Newton's second law (here in static) written with continuum mechanics variables :

$$\sigma_{ij,j} + f_i = 0 \quad \text{momentum balance} \quad (3)$$

with f_i the sum of the volumic forces.

A third equation describing the material behaviour (i.e. the relation between ϵ and σ) is also needed to solve the problem. As the media is considered as homogeneous, isotropic and following a linear elastic behaviour, the equation writes :

$$\sigma_{ij} = \lambda \delta_{ij} \epsilon_{kk} + 2\mu \epsilon_{ij} \quad \text{linear elasticity} \quad (4)$$

Where λ and μ are the Lamé coefficients that parameterize the elastic relation.

Knowing these equations, it is possible, for any given displacement field, to calculate the corresponding stress field and check if the momentum balance is verified. We will follow this path to impose the equations as a soft constraint on PINNs.

1.2.2 Imposing continuum mechanics on PINNs

The PINN is used to model the displacement according to the spatial coordinates $x : \mathcal{N}(x) = \tilde{u}$. Thanks to automatic differentiation, it is possible to seamlessly compute \tilde{u} derivatives and therefore compute the corresponding strain $\tilde{\epsilon}$ and stress $\tilde{\sigma}$ using equations 4 and 2. For \tilde{u} to respect the physics prior it would then be necessary that $\tilde{\sigma}$ respect the momentum balance 3. It is thus possible to construct a loss term \mathcal{L}_{PDE} that measures the adequation of a given PINN prediction \tilde{u} to continuum mechanics equations :

$$\mathcal{L}_{PDE} = \sum_{\tilde{\sigma} \in \Omega} \|\tilde{\sigma}_{ij,j} + f_i\| \quad (5)$$

with $\|\cdot\|$ a norm operator (e.g. euclidean norm).

It is still necessary to impose boundary conditions on the neural network. A simple way to handle this is to add a boundary residual term \mathcal{L}_{BC} to the loss function. The idea is to sample the boundary domain and to compare the PINN prediction to the imposed boundary condition value $u_{BC}(X)$:

$$\mathcal{L}_{BC} = \sum_{X \in \partial\Omega} (\mathcal{N}(X) - u_{BC}(X))^2$$

This equation is written for boundary condition in displacement but it is possible to take the stress ones into account the same way, simply by replacing the displacement by the corresponding stress.

We end up with total loss function composed of three terms : $\mathcal{L}_{total} = \mathcal{L}_u + \mathcal{L}_{PDE} + \mathcal{L}_{BC}$.

Thus, if the training is successful (i.e., if the loss is close to zero), the PINN will both predict training data and be consistent with the physics described by the PDE and the boundary conditions. This PINN architecture is summarized in figure 1.

Figure 1: The PINN framework for a boundary value problem

1.3 PINNs implementation of the problem

The general architecture of PINNs is presented in the previous section. However, in order to adequately address our specific problem, several modifications and refinements have been made taking into account the literature and our own experimentation. Starting from the results obtained in [6] and following the advice from [7], we implement two different neural networks \mathcal{N}_{x1} and \mathcal{N}_{x2} trained simultaneously to reconstruct respectively each direction of the displacement field.

The prediction term \mathcal{L}_u in the loss function can be useful when the material properties are unknown and need to be inferred from experimental data. This term is therefore absent for this first example since it is a direct boundary value problem.

Instead of using the norm of the PDE as a loss for the backpropagation during training, we compute the strain energy integrated all over the domain :

$$W(\tilde{\epsilon}, \tilde{\sigma}) = \frac{1}{2} \iiint_{\Omega} \tilde{\epsilon} : \tilde{\sigma} \quad (6)$$

As the solution displacement field corresponds to the minimum deformation energy, it can be used as a training loss. Using a derived energy form instead of the absolute value of the PDE is often a good idea because it is physically interpretable and can provide better convergence in practice.[7]

As mentioned in the previous section, boundary conditions can be enforced in a soft way with an extra loss term. In practice this method often causes problems of convergence during training because the different terms combined in the loss can be of different magnitudes. That's the reason why hard constraints are preferred when possible. The idea is to pass the output of the PINN to an "ad hoc" function that will ensure a priori compliance with boundary conditions.

This implementation allows not to worry about the boundary conditions during the training phase and, although the need to find a different "ad hoc" function for each problem may seem limiting, this approach is generalizable to more complex domains as shown in [8].

Finally, the loss function is composed of only one term : $\mathcal{L}_{total} = W(\epsilon, \sigma)$.

An overview of the final algorithmic architecture is given in figure 2.

Figure 2: Architecture finally adopted for the PINN implementation of the problem

2 Numerical application

The PINNs developed here are intended to be used with DIC measurements in future research. As this technology only measures surface displacements, we have chosen for this numerical application a boundary value problem in the 2D unit square ($\Omega = [0, 1] \times [0, 1]$) with only in-plane displacements : $u = \begin{pmatrix} u_1 \\ u_2 \end{pmatrix}$

Thanks to symmetry, strain and stress tensors depends on only 3 variables and can be written as vectors :

$$\sigma = \begin{pmatrix} \sigma_{11} \\ \sigma_{22} \\ \sigma_{12} \end{pmatrix} \quad ; \quad \epsilon = \begin{pmatrix} \epsilon_{11} \\ \epsilon_{22} \\ \epsilon_{12} \end{pmatrix} \quad (7)$$

The volumetric force f_i is neglected here. In order to obtain realistic orders of magnitude, elastic parameters are set closed to silicon rubber ones with a Young modulus of 50 MPa and a Poisson ratio of 0.5, corresponding to the following Lamé coefficients : $\lambda = 133.3 \text{ kPa}$; $\mu = 333.3 \text{ kPa}$

We impose the following boundary condition in displacement on the vertical edges of the domain :

$$u_1(x_1 = 0) = 0 \quad ; \quad u_1(x_1 = 1) = 0.5 \text{ m}$$

This boundary conditions can be imposed to the PINN using the following "ad hoc" transformation :

$$\begin{cases} u_{x1}(x_1, x_2) = \delta - \delta(1 - x_1) + x_1(1 - x_1)\mathcal{N}_{x1}(x_1, x_2) \\ u_{x2}(x_1, x_2) = x_1(1 - x_1)\mathcal{N}_{x2}(x_1, x_2) \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

with $\delta = 0.5 \text{ m}$ the horizontal displacement on the right edge of the domain.

The results of the method developed in this work will be compared to a reference finite element solution computed with a mesh of $100 * 100$ elements. For convenience, since the neural network implementation is made in python, the FEM solution is computed using scikit-fem [9] python framework, the displacement field obtained is shown on figure 3

Figure 3: Finite element reference solution of the problem

The stochastic gradient descent algorithm Adam [10] is used for the training process. The code is written in python with the PyTorch framework.

2.1 First results and comparison with the FEM solution

The two feedforward neural networks \mathcal{N}_{x1} and \mathcal{N}_{x2} have 6 hidden layers of size 50×50 , the input size is 2 (for the two space dimensions) and the output size is one (one direction of the displacement).

The PINN is trained using the Adam algorithm with a batch size of 20 samples chosen randomly at each of

the 5000 iterations (number of epochs) with a learning rate of 1×10^{-4} . The loss history during the training is reported in figure 4.

Figure 4: Feedforward PINN loss history during training

The loss decrease until the 3000th iteration with no significant improvement after, indicating that the local minimum is reached. Given that the strain energy reached is closed to the FEM one, we can expect a good displacement reconstruction from the neural network.

Another important remark is that persistent variation of the loss is mainly due to the random sampling strategy. Thus the comparison between the loss and the FEM strain is limited because the loss is only computed on 20 random points whereas the FEM strain energy is computed all over the domain on 10000 points. A better metric is the PINN strain energy calculated on the same points as the FEM one. Here are the values reached at the end of the training :

- FEM strain energy : 1631.89 J
- PINN strain energy : 1635.98 J
- Loss strain energy : 1633.12 J

A significant difference can be observed between the loss and the PINN strain energy. This observation encourages the use of a larger sample size during training as the sample isn't representative enough of the global strain energy. The displacement predicted by the PINN is shown in figure 5.

Figure 5: Displacement fields reconstructed by the trained feedforward PINNs

The predicted displacement seems close to the FEM reference solution. For a better comparison, the difference between the two solutions is displayed as a heatmap on figure 6.

Figure 6: Distance between the feedforward PINN and FEM solutions

Several conclusions can be drawn from the first result.

First, the residual is not a white noise, some shape corresponding to a specific spatial variation frequency are clearly visible, as if the PINN reconstructed a first mode of the answer but missed the second one. One possible answer proposed in [6] is the fact that ANN fail to reconstruct high order spatial variation. A possible solution introduced in [11] is to add Fourier features to the input space. This is a data augmentation technique consisting in applying sinusoidal function of various frequency to the inputs and to use the result as extra input variables. This is creating high frequency spatial variation in the input space and thus allows high frequency reconstruction for the ANN.

Then global metrics, such as determination coefficient R^2 , seems to indicate good reconstruction :

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum(\tilde{u} - u_{FEM})^2}{\sum(u_{FEM} - u_{FEM})^2} \quad (9)$$

Which gives for each direction : $R_{u1}^2 = 0.9993$ and $R_{u2}^2 = 0.9833$

Nevertheless, the fact that the residuals are localised on specific shapes motivates the search for a more complex architecture to better capture the behaviour. A possible improvement proposed in [6] is to use a residual network (ResNet) instead of a simple feedforward architecture.

Indeed, as networks becomes deeper, the convergence can be blocked by the vanishing gradient problem. The gradient computed by automatic differentiation tends to zero and the weights and biases of the network are no longer updated during backpropagation. The ResNet mitigates this issue by adding skip connection between layers to directly retro-propagate the loss without passing throw the automatic differentiation and can thus allow better convergence. [12]

The following subsection presents the results obtained for a ResNet architecture with and without Fourier features.

2.2 The ResNet architecture and Fourier features

In order to fairly compare their performance, the ResNet networks are chosen with same amount of trainable parameters than the feedforward one. The optimization step also remains unchanged, i.e an Adam optimizer with the same parameters. The loss history of the three networks (feedforward, ResNet with and without Fourier features) are shown in figure 7.

Figure 7: Comparison of PINNs loss history during training

The figure illustrates that the Res-Net architecture significantly improves convergence of the example studied. To compare each final solution to the FEM reference, we compute energy of the residual strain :

$$\mathcal{D}(\epsilon_a, \epsilon_b) = W(\epsilon_a - \epsilon_b, \sigma_a - \sigma_b) = \frac{1}{2} \iiint_{\Omega} \delta \epsilon : \delta \sigma \quad (10)$$

The different global metrics of the solutions are summarized in table 1 :

Table 1: Comparison of the networks with several metrics in joule.

Network	Strain Energy	Energy distance to FEM
Feedforward	1635.98	12.24
ResNet	1634.53	9.51
ResNet-Fourier	1633.69	8.91
FEM reference	1631.89	0

As expected, better results are achieved using the ResNet architecture and adding Fourier features regarding strain energy and distance to FEM. Figures 8 and 9 show the spatial distribution of the residuals over the domain.

Figure 8: Distance between ResNet and FEM solutions

Figure 9: Distance between ResNet-Fourier and FEM solutions

The same pattern as the feedforward network are visible for the ResNet residuals but they partly disappear for the ResNet-Fourier.

Accordingly to the previous remark, we decided to carry on the training for the Fourier-ResNet architecture with a larger sampling size of 2000 points. The network manage to reach a strain energy of 1631.55 J, just below the FEM one. The energy distance to the FEM is 4.44 J, the spacial distribution of the residual is shown in figure 10.

Figure 10: Distance between FEM and ResNet-Fourier trained with a sample size of 2000

Some distinct residual regions are still present at the corners of the domain, but it is hard to tell whether it is the PINN or the FEM that is inaccurate as FE models are known to be potentially inaccurate at the edge of the domain. A way to overcome this difficulty could be to compute the exact solution using complex variable methods, this is still work in progress.

Conclusion

In this paper, we have illustrated how the general PINN framework can be applied to a boundary problem in continuum mechanics. A specific architecture of two distinct networks \mathcal{N}_{x_1} and \mathcal{N}_{x_2} as well as the use of strain energy as a loss function have been motivated. The proposed models were successfully implemented and compared to a finite element model. The final model using a ResNet model and Fourier features achieved a displacement reconstruction of comparable accuracy to the finite element model. These results encourage further application of ResNet for inverse quantification of material properties where it could be used as an advantageous alternative to finite element model updating for example.

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References

- [1] M. Raissi, P. Perdikaris, and G. Karniadakis, “Physics-informed neural networks: A deep learning framework for solving forward and inverse problems involving nonlinear partial differential equations,” *Journal of Computational Physics*, vol. 378, pp. 686–707, Feb. 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0021999118307125>
- [2] G. Cybenko, “Approximation by superpositions of a sigmoidal function,” *Mathematics of Control, Signals and Systems*, vol. 2, no. 4, pp. 303–314, Dec. 1989. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02551274>
- [3] A. Paszke, S. Gross, F. Massa, A. Lerer, J. Bradbury, G. Chanan, T. Killeen, Z. Lin, N. Gimelshein, L. Antiga, A. Desmaison, A. Kopf, E. Yang, Z. DeVito, M. Raison, A. Tejani, S. Chilamkurthy, B. Steiner, L. Fang, J. Bai, and S. Chintala, “Pytorch: An imperative style, high-performance deep learning library,” in *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems 32*. Curran Associates, Inc., 2019, pp. 8024–8035. [Online]. Available: <http://papers.nips.cc/paper/9015-pytorch-an-imperative-style-high-performance-deep-learning-library.pdf>
- [4] M. Abadi, A. Agarwal, P. Barham, E. Brevdo, Z. Chen, C. Citro, G. S. Corrado, A. Davis, J. Dean, M. Devin, S. Ghemawat, I. Goodfellow, A. Harp, G. Irving, M. Isard, Y. Jia, R. Jozefowicz, L. Kaiser, M. Kudlur, J. Levenberg, D. Mané, R. Monga, S. Moore, D. Murray, C. Olah, M. Schuster, J. Shlens, B. Steiner, I. Sutskever, K. Talwar, P. Tucker, V. Vanhoucke, V. Vasudevan, F. Viégas, O. Vinyals, P. Warden, M. Wattenberg, M. Wicke, Y. Yu, and X. Zheng, “TensorFlow: Large-scale machine learning on heterogeneous systems,” 2015, software available from tensorflow.org. [Online]. Available: <https://www.tensorflow.org/>
- [5] C. C. Aggarwal, “An Introduction to Neural Networks,” in *Neural Networks and Deep Learning: A Textbook*, C. C. Aggarwal, Ed. Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2018, pp. 1–52. [Online]. Available: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-94463-0_1
- [6] A. Hans, “A Hands-on Introduction to Physics-Informed Neural Networks,” 2021.
- [7] E. Haghighat, M. Raissi, A. Moure, H. Gomez, and R. Juanes, “A deep learning framework for solution and discovery in solid mechanics,” *arXiv:2003.02751 [cs, stat]*, May 2020, arXiv: 2003.02751. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/2003.02751>
- [8] N. Sukumar and A. Srivastava, “Exact imposition of boundary conditions with distance functions in physics-informed deep neural networks,” *Computer Methods in Applied Mechanics and Engineering*, vol. 389, p. 114333, Feb. 2022, arXiv: 2104.08426. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/2104.08426>
- [9] T. Gustafsson and G. D. McBain, “scikit-fem: A python package for finite element assembly,” *Journal of Open Source Software*, vol. 5, no. 52, p. 2369, 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.21105/joss.02369>
- [10] D. P. Kingma and J. Ba, “Adam: A Method for Stochastic Optimization,” Dec. 2014. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/1412.6980v9>
- [11] M. Tancik, P. P. Srinivasan, B. Mildenhall, S. Fridovich-Keil, N. Raghavan, U. Singhal, R. Ramamoorthi, J. T. Barron, and R. Ng, “Fourier features let networks learn high frequency functions in low dimensional domains,” 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2006.10739>
- [12] K. He, X. Zhang, S. Ren, and J. Sun, “Deep residual learning for image recognition,” 2015. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/1512.03385>